

GREEN JUSTICE AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS: INTEGRATING ISLAMIC ENVIRONMENTAL ETHICS INTO RELIGIOUS EDUCATION

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Environmental degradation and climate injustice have emerged as pressing global challenges that threaten social equity and sustainable development. In response to these crises, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) emphasize environmental justice, ethical governance, and inclusive education as key pillars for global sustainability. This study explores the role of Islamic Religious Education (IRE) in promoting green justice by integrating Islamic environmental ethics into educational frameworks aligned with the SDGs. Drawing upon the concepts of khalīfah fī al-ard (human stewardship of the earth), amānah (trust), mīzān (balance), and the prohibition of fasād (environmental destruction), this research employs a normative-qualitative approach through textual analysis of Qur'anic verses, prophetic traditions, and classical as well as contemporary Islamic scholarship. These principles are then critically connected to relevant SDGs, particularly SDG 4 (Quality Education), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions). The findings indicate that Islamic Religious Education possesses significant potential to function as a transformative medium for cultivating environmental consciousness, ethical responsibility, and sustainable behavior among learners. By embedding green justice values into religious education curricula, IRE can contribute to shaping environmentally responsible citizens and future leaders committed to sustainability and social justice. This study argues that the integration of Islamic environmental ethics into education not only strengthens the moral foundation of environmental governance but also positions Islamic education as a vital contributor to global sustainability discourse.

Keywords: Environmental Ethics, Sustainability, Islamic Religious Education, Green Justice, Sustainable Development Goals.